

FORMATION OF COMPLEX COMPOUNDS BETWEEN CADMIUM HALIDES
AND ALKALI HALIDES. PART I. SYSTEM $\text{CdCl}_2\text{—NH}_4\text{Cl—H}_2\text{O}$

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The formation of complex compounds between CdCl_2 and NH_4Cl has been studied by the conductivity, density, viscosity and *P. P.* methods. The graphs obtained by all the methods show six breaks at exactly the same points, showing the formation of six complexes, namely, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 4\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 3\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $3\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ and $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, of which $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 3\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ and $3\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ have not been reported earlier.

Cadmium chloride is known to form double or complex salts with ammonium chloride in the solid state or in solution. Wittstein (*Buchner's Report*, 1837, 87, 32) and Von Hauer (*Sitzber. Akad. Wien*, 1854, 13, 449) were the first to observe that cadmium oxide, hydroxide or carbonate dissolved in a solution of ammonium chloride with evolution of ammonia, and on evaporation the solution furnished crystals with very variable proportions of ammonium and cadmium chlorides. Von Hauer isolated the hexachloride, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 4\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, from the solution. Following this observation various workers tried to prepare the different cadmium ammonium chlorides and the compounds $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 4\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ and $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ were reported.

EXPERIMENTAL

The substances used were of A. R. quality. Stock solutions of cadmium chloride and ammonium chloride were prepared by dissolving the calculated amounts of the respective salts in conductivity water to form *M/4* solutions. The method of Nayer and Pande (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 27A, 286) of keeping the concentration of one of the constituents constant and varying the other systematically was adopted to prepare the subsequent solutions. In this case the concentration of ammonium chloride was kept constant and varying amounts of cadmium chloride were added. Every time the solution was made up to 50 c. c. in a standard flask with conductivity water. In this way 35 mixed solutions were prepared and subjected to study by the conductivity, density and freezing point measurements. The results are shown graphically. From the graph it can be seen that six definite breaks are obtained by all the three methods at exactly the same points, showing the existence in solution of the compounds $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 4\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 3\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$, $3\text{CdCl}_2\cdot 2\text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$ and $2\text{CdCl}_2\cdot \text{NH}_4\text{Cl}$. Of these, only those with ratios 1 : 4, 1 : 2, 3 : 1 and 2 : 1 have been reported earlier. The other two appear to be new compounds.

FIG. 1

Additional work as proof for the existence of these compounds is being done by E.M.F. measurements and absorption spectra studies. Efforts are also being made to isolate the compounds, if possible.

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